

Accounting Functions and Tax Strategy for the Real Estate Investor

By Michael Martin

Disclaimer: This article is for educational purposes and is not legal, tax, or investment advice. Investors should consult a qualified tax professional regarding their specific facts.

To my sons: Mikah, Elijah, and Levi

John 3:16

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Accounting Functions

Accounting is the language of business. The cash basis of accounting means recording transactions when cash is received or paid. For our first case, let's assume a single investor seeking to invest in residential real estate. What are the accounting entries required? In the three accounting cases that follow, case 1 assumes an investment without a mortgage, case 2 assumes an investment with a mortgage, and case 3 assumes a partnership.

An entity for buying and holding residential real estate is a limited liability company (LLC). For example, an investor may establish an LLC named 123 Anywhere Arizona LLC by filing Articles of Organization with the Arizona Corporation Commission. The investor will then obtain an employer identification number (EIN) from the Internal Revenue Service (IRS). The investor will need to open a bank account, which requires the LLC and EIN documents. An operating agreement serves to outline the legal rules of the LLC.

Case 1 fact pattern (without a mortgage):

1. Open bank account with \$50
2. Contribute capital of \$500,000.
3. Acquire residential real estate for \$500,000.
4. Allocate 80% of real estate to building at \$400,000 (the allocation is based on square footage)
5. Allocate 20% of real estate to land at \$100,000 (assumes land is 20% of square footage)
6. Receive rental income of \$2,800 per month (show only 1 entry for demonstration purposes)
7. Contribute capital of \$5,000.
8. Pay for new air conditioning (AC) unit for \$5,000.
9. Pay real estate taxes of \$2,850.
10. Pay property insurance of \$500.
11. Record depreciation of \$14,545 for building.
12. Record depreciation of \$182 for AC unit.
13. Distribute profit from rental activity \$27,450.

Accounting Journal Entries:

Date	Account and Description	Debit	Credit
01/15/2024	Cash	\$50	
	Capital Contributions		\$50
	To record cash contributed to open bank account		
01/20/2024	Cash	\$500,000	
	Capital Contributions		\$500,000
	To record cash contributed to investing in real estate		
01/21/2024	Building	\$400,000	
	Land	\$100,000	
	Cash		\$500,000
	To record investment in building and land		

Date	Account and Description	Debit	Credit
02/01/2024	Cash	\$2,800	
	Rental Income		\$2,800
	To record rent received		
06/15/2024	Cash	\$5,000	
	Capital Contributions		\$5,000
	To record cash contributed to purchase new AC unit		
06/16/2024	AC System	\$5,000	
	Cash		\$5,000
	To record purchase of AC unit		
06/30/2024	Real Estate Taxes	\$2,850	
	Cash		\$2,850
	To record payment of real estate taxes		
06/30/2024	Insurance	\$500	
	Cash		\$500
	To record payment of insurance		
12/31/2024	Depreciation Expense	\$14,545	
	Accumulated Depreciation		\$14,545
	To record depreciation on building		
12/31/2024	Depreciation Expense	\$182	
	Accumulated Depreciation		\$182
	To record depreciation on AC system		
12/31/2024	Capital Distributions	\$27,450	
	Cash		\$27,450
	To record distribution of profit from rental activity		

Financial Statements:

For purposes of this article, I will consider the balance sheet and income statement¹. These financial statements may be used for internal management as well as external requirements. External requirements may be when applying for a loan and the bank requires financial statements to determine eligibility.

The financial statements below are compiled from the case fact pattern and accounting entries. The balance sheet presents the fundamental accounting equation, which is stated as assets equals liabilities plus equity. Below you can see the total assets are 490,323 with zero liabilities and 490,323 in equity. Assets are positive because they are debits, with exception of contra assets. Liabilities are negative because they are credits, with exception of contra liabilities. Equity is negative because it is a credit, with exception of contra equity.

123 Anywhere Arizona LLC
Balance Sheet
As of December 31, 2024

Assets	
Cash	\$ 50
Fixed Assets	
Building	\$ 400,000
Land	\$ 100,000
AC System	\$ 5,000
Accumulated Depreciation	<u>\$ (14,727)</u>
Total Fixed Assets	<u>\$ 490,273</u>
Total Assets	<u><u>\$ 490,323</u></u>
Liabilities and Member's Equity	
Liabilities	\$ -
Member's Equity	
Capital Contributions	\$ (505,050)
Capital Distributions	\$ 27,450
Net Profit	<u>\$ (12,723)</u>
Total Member's Equity	<u>\$ (490,323)</u>
Total Liabilities and Member's Equity	<u><u>\$ (490,323)</u></u>

¹ For purposes of this article, certain financial statement amounts are presented from a debit-credit/trial balance perspective. Under this presentation, debit-balance accounts, such as assets and expenses, appear as positive amounts, while credit-balance accounts, such as liabilities, equity, revenue, and net profit, appear as negative amounts. This format is used to illustrate how the journal entries flow into the financial statements and to show the underlying accounting mechanics. In traditional investor-facing financial statement presentation, liabilities, equity, revenue, and net income are generally presented as positive amounts, unless otherwise indicated, and the balance sheet is commonly presented under the accounting equation: Assets = Liabilities + Equity.

Below is the income statement². This financial report is sometimes called profit and loss. However, since there is a profit in this case, it is called an income statement. If it were a loss, then it would be called a statement of operations. This statement shows income minus expenses to arrive at profit or loss. Income is presented as negative because it is a credit. Expenses are positive because they are debits. Profit is negative because income is greater than expenses.

123 Anywhere Arizona LLC

Income Statement

For the 12 Months Ended December 31, 2024

Rental Income	\$ (30,800)
Expenses	
Real Estate Taxes	\$ 2,850
Insurance	\$ 500
Depreciation Expense	<u>\$ 14,727</u>
Total Expenses	<u>\$ 18,077</u>
Profit	<u>\$ (12,723)</u>

² For purposes of this article, the term “income statement” is used when the activity results in net income, while “statement of operations” is used when the activity results in a net loss. This terminology is used to emphasize that the report still reflects operating activity even where operations do not produce positive net income. In general accounting usage, “income statement,” “profit and loss statement,” and “statement of operations” are often used interchangeably.

Case 2 fact pattern (with a mortgage):

1. Open bank account with \$50
2. Obtain a mortgage of \$500,000 with a \$101,000 down payment.
3. Acquire residential real estate for \$500,000
4. Allocate 80% of real estate to building for \$400,000.
5. Allocate 20% of real estate to land at \$100,000.
6. Receive rental income of \$2,800 per month (show only 1 entry for demonstration purposes)
7. Record escrow activity with a mortgage payment of \$2,217 (show only 1 entry)
8. Contribute capital of \$5,000.
9. Pay for new air conditioning (AC) unit for \$5,000.
10. Record adjustment for real estate taxes of 2,850.
11. Record adjustment for property insurance of \$500.
12. Record depreciation of \$14,545 for building.
13. Record depreciation of \$182 for AC unit.
14. Distribute cash flow from rental activity \$6,413.

Accounting Journal Entries:

Date	Account and Description	Debit	Credit
01/15/2024	Cash	\$50	
	Capital Contributions		\$50
	To record cash contributed to open bank account		
01/15/2024	Building	\$400,000	
	Land	\$100,000	
	Escrow	\$1,000	
	Mortgage Payable		\$400,000
	Capital Contributions		\$101,000
	To record acquisition of real estate with mortgage		
02/01/2024	Cash	\$2,800	
	Rental Income		\$2,800
	To record rental income received		
02/07/2024	Mortgage Payable	\$563	
	Interest Expense	\$1,375	
	Escrow	\$279	
	Cash		\$2,217
	To record mortgage payment		
06/15/2024	Cash	\$5,000	
	Capital Contributions		\$5,000
	To record cash contributed to purchase new AC unit		

Date	Account and Description	Debit	Credit
06/16/2024	AC System	\$5,000	
	Cash		\$5,000
	To record purchase of AC unit		
12/31/2024	Real Estate Taxes	\$2,850	
	Escrow		\$2,850
	To record adjustment for real estate taxes		
12/31/2024	Insurance	\$500	
	Escrow		\$500
	To record adjustment for insurance		
12/31/2024	Depreciation Expense	\$14,545	
	Accumulated Depreciation		\$14,545
	To record depreciation on building		
12/31/2024	Depreciation Expense	\$182	
	Accumulated Depreciation		\$182
	To record depreciation on AC system		
12/31/2024	Capital Distributions	\$6,413	
	Cash		\$6,413
	To record distribution of cash flow from rental activity		

Financial Statements:

123 Anywhere Arizona LLC

Balance Sheet

As of December 31, 2024

Assets

Current Assets

Cash \$ 50

Escrow \$ 719

Total Current Assets \$ 769

Fixed Assets

Building \$ 400,000

Land \$ 100,000

AC System \$ 5,000

Accumulated Depreciation \$ (14,727)

Total Fixed Assets \$ 490,273

Total Assets \$ 491,042

Liabilities and Member's Equity

Liabilities - Mortgage Payable \$ (393,807)

Member's Equity

Capital Contributions \$ (106,050)

Capital Distributions \$ 6,413

Net Loss \$ 2,402

Total Member's Equity \$ (97,235)

Total Liabilities and Member's Equity \$ (491,042)

123 Anywhere Arizona LLC

Statement of Operations

For the 12 Months Ended December 31, 2024

Rental Income \$ (30,800)

Expenses

Interest Expense \$ 15,125

Real Estate Taxes \$ 2,850

Insurance \$ 500

Depreciation Expense \$ 14,727

Total Expenses \$ 33,202

Loss \$ 2,402

Case 3 fact pattern (partnership with mortgage):

1. Open bank account with \$150
2. Obtain a mortgage of \$500,000 with a \$101,000 down payment.
3. Acquire residential real estate for \$500,000
4. Allocate 80% of real estate to building for \$400,000.
5. Allocate 20% of real estate to land at \$100,000.
6. Receive rental income of \$2,800 per month (show only 1 entry for demonstration purposes)
7. Record escrow activity with a mortgage payment of \$2,217 (show only 1 entry)
8. Contribute capital of \$5,000.
9. Pay for new air conditioning (AC) unit for \$5,000.
10. Record adjustment for real estate taxes of 2,850.
11. Record adjustment for property insurance of \$500.
12. Record depreciation of \$14,545 for building.
13. Record depreciation of \$182 for AC unit.
14. Distribute cash flow from rental activity \$6,413.

Accounting Journal Entries:

Date	Account and Description	Debit	Credit
01/15/2024	Cash	\$150	
	Investor 1, Capital Contributions		\$50
	Investor 2, Capital Contributions		\$50
	Investor 3, Capital Contributions		\$50
	To record cash contributed to open bank account		
01/15/2024	Building	\$400,000	
	Land	\$100,000	
	Escrow	\$1,000	
	Mortgage Payable		\$400,000
	Investor 1, Capital Contributions		\$33,666
	Investor 2, Capital Contributions		\$33,667
	Investor 3, Capital Contributions		\$33,667
	To record acquisition of real estate with mortgage		
02/01/2024	Cash	\$2,800	
	Rental Income		\$2,800
	To record rental income received		
02/07/2024	Mortgage Payable	\$563	
	Interest Expense	\$1,375	
	Escrow	\$279	
	Cash		\$2,217
	To record mortgage payment		

Date	Account and Description	Debit	Credit
06/15/2024	Cash	\$5,000	
	Investor 1, Capital Contributions		\$1,666
	Investor 2, Capital Contributions		\$1,667
	Investor 3, Capital Contributions		\$1,667
	To record cash contributed to purchase new AC unit		
06/16/2024	AC System	\$5,000	
	Cash		\$5,000
	To record purchase of AC unit		
12/31/2024	Real Estate Taxes	\$2,850	
	Escrow		\$2,850
	To record adjustment for real estate taxes		
12/31/2024	Insurance	\$500	
	Escrow		\$500
	To record adjustment for insurance		
12/31/2024	Depreciation Expense	\$14,545	
	Accumulated Depreciation		\$14,545
	To record depreciation on building		
12/31/2024	Depreciation Expense	\$182	
	Accumulated Depreciation		\$182
	To record depreciation on AC system		
12/31/2024	Investor 1, Capital Distributions	\$2,138	
	Investor 2, Capital Distributions	\$2,138	
	Investor 3, Capital Distributions	\$2,137	
	Cash		\$6,413
	To record distribution of profit from rental activity		

Financial Statements:

123 Anywhere Arizona LLC

Balance Sheet

As of December 31, 2024

Assets

Current Assets

Cash	\$	150
Escrow	\$	719
Total Current Assets	\$	<u>869</u>

Fixed Assets

Building	\$	400,000
Land	\$	100,000
AC System	\$	5,000
Accumulated Depreciation	\$	<u>(14,727)</u>
Total Fixed Assets	\$	<u>490,273</u>
Total Assets	\$	<u><u>491,142</u></u>

Liabilities and Members' Equity

Liabilities - Mortgage Payable	\$	(393,807)
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Members' Equity

Investor 1, Capital Contributions	\$	(35,382)
Investor 2, Capital Contributions	\$	(35,384)
Investor 3, Capital Contributions	\$	(35,384)
Investor 1, Capital Distributions	\$	2,138
Investor 2, Capital Distributions	\$	2,138
Investor 3, Capital Distributions	\$	2,137
Net Loss	\$	<u>2,402</u>
Total Members' Equity	\$	<u>(97,335)</u>
Total Liabilities and Members' Equity	\$	<u><u>(491,142)</u></u>

Financial Statements (Continued):

123 Anywhere Arizona LLC

Statement of Operations

For the 12 Months Ended December 31, 2024

Rental Income \$ (30,800)

Expenses

Interest Expense \$ 15,125

Real Estate Taxes \$ 2,850

Insurance \$ 500

Depreciation Expense \$ 14,727

Total Expenses \$ 33,202

Loss \$ 2,402

Real Estate Tax Strategy

An investor is seeking to invest in the real estate market to buy and hold rental properties. Rental properties may create tax-advantaged results which are called paper losses. Although, a rental property may have a statement of loss, where the expenses are greater than the income, it may be due to depreciation³ expense, and the actual cash flow may be positive.

If a real estate investment creates statements of losses over time, the after-tax cash flow may be positive. While depreciation is an expense, it is a non-cash deduction. It is possible to reduce your tax liability by offsetting income with depreciation losses. Consider the following hypothetical situation:

An investor buys and holds one rental property with \$4,000 in cash flow at the end of year. When his accountant prepares the taxes and calculates depreciation on the building, the deduction for depreciation is \$20,000. As a result, the cash flow, minus the depreciation, is a paper loss of \$16,000. Assuming a 32% tax rate, the tax savings is \$5,120. Consequently, the annual cash flow is really \$9,120. So, while the investor created a paper loss, the actual cash flow is more than doubled from this tax strategy. The tax benefits yielded from paper losses depend on whether the investor can currently deduct the loss under passive activity rules.

The concept of depreciation entails spreading the acquisition costs of property over the useful life of the asset. Congress determines useful life of assets. For instance, residential real estate property has a useful life of 27.5 years, and commercial real estate property has a useful life of 39 years. The size of the property is not a factor in determining residential or commercial assets. The nature of the asset determines its useful life. A large apartment development is larger than a 100 square foot office suite, but the apartments are residential in nature, and the office suite is commercial in nature.

An important distinction is the building and land. While the building is depreciated, land is not. In depreciation calculations, land is subtracted from the acquisition cost of the property to arrive at an adjusted basis for the building. Measurements of land and building square footage should be used to determine appropriate allocation of the acquisition cost. To calculate the annual depreciation, the adjusted basis is divided by the useful life. Monthly depreciation is calculated by dividing the annual depreciation by 12.

Alternatively, a building has components which may be identified to assign a different useful life. In addition, an investor may improve the land, which may have a different useful life. Identifying the various components of the building and land improvements is tax advantageous because the useful life may be shorter, which allows for an accelerated depreciation method. In addition, there are bonus depreciation⁴ and section 179 depreciation⁵ methods available to allow for greater deductions in the year of purchase. A cost segregation study may be used to identify the engineering of the building components and their respective useful lives.

³ Internal Revenue Code § 167, "Depreciation," U.S. Code, Title 26, <https://www.law.cornell.edu/uscode/text/26/167>.

⁴ Internal Revenue Code § 168(k), "Additional First-Year Depreciation Allowance," U.S. Code, Title 26, <https://www.law.cornell.edu/uscode/text/26/168#k>.

⁵ Internal Revenue Code § 179, "Election to Expense Certain Depreciable Business Assets," U.S. Code, Title 26, <https://www.law.cornell.edu/uscode/text/26/179>.

The IRS has a de minimis rule⁶ that enables an investor to set an accounting policy to expense items that cost \$2,500 or less. This means that an investor may bypass the depreciation accounting, and expense the cost of improvements at the threshold of \$2,500 or less, per item. If an investor pays \$4,900 for 7 windows at a cost of \$700 per window, then the total cost of \$4,900 may be expensed because each window is less than \$2,500.

There are a few different kinds of income under the IRS code. Under the code, income may be either earned, portfolio, or passive. With respect to our current analysis, profit from rental properties is considered passive. Losses derived from passive profit motives may be deducted against other passive activities⁷. Losses not used may be carried forward in future years. In sales transactions, losses are allowed to be deducted in the year of sales. Exceptions exist with respect to the loss rules mentioned above for rental properties. An active investor in rental properties may take a deduction for losses up to \$25,000, but a phase out process starts when adjusted gross income is \$100,000. If adjusted gross income is \$150,000 there is no deduction allowed. If the investor spends at least 750 hours annually on managing rental properties, in which the time spent is greater than other sources of income, then they are treated as a Real Estate Professional⁸, in which case the loss limitations mentioned above do not apply.

In this case 4, we consider a real estate syndication, which is a kind of larger partnership that creates an opportunity for multiple investors to pool capital to acquire large properties, such as an office building, that would normally be too expensive for one person or small partnership. In this case, we consider a mid-sized syndicate with 100 partners.

Case 4 fact pattern (syndicate partnership with mortgage):

1. Open bank account with \$10,050,000 with \$100,500 from each investor (100 partners).
2. Obtain a mortgage of \$50,000,000 with a \$10,050,000 down payment.
3. Acquire commercial real estate for \$50,000,000
4. Allocate 80% of real estate to building for \$40,000,000.
5. Allocate 20% of real estate to land at \$10,000,000.
6. Engage consulting firm for \$15,000 to conduct cost segregation study
7. Receive rental income of \$400,000 per month (show only 1 entry)
8. Record escrow activity with a mortgage payment of \$383,859.61 (show only 1 entry)
9. Contribute capital of \$50,000.
10. Pay for new air conditioning (AC) system for \$50,000.
11. Record adjustment for real estate taxes of \$350,000.
12. Record adjustment for property insurance of \$75,000.
13. Record depreciation of \$2,654,907 for building.
14. Record depreciation of \$50,000 for AC system.
15. Distribute cash flow from rental activity \$150,000.

⁶ Treasury Regulation § 1.263(a)-1(f), "Amounts Paid to Acquire or Produce Tangible Property: De Minimis Safe Harbor Election," Code of Federal Regulations, Title 26, [https://www.law.cornell.edu/cfr/text/26/1.263\(a\)-1#f](https://www.law.cornell.edu/cfr/text/26/1.263(a)-1#f).

⁷ Internal Revenue Code § 469, "Passive Activity Losses and Credits Limited," U.S. Code, Title 26, <https://www.law.cornell.edu/uscode/text/26/469>.

⁸ Internal Revenue Code § 469(c)(7), "Special Rules for Real Estate Professionals," U.S. Code, Title 26, https://www.law.cornell.edu/uscode/text/26/469#c_7.

16. Below is amortization schedule for year 1:

Interest Assumptions:

Compounding Period: Monthly

Nominal Annual Rate: 6.500%

Cash Flow Data - Loans and Payments

	Event	Date	Amount	Number	Period	End Date
1	Loan	01/15/2026	40,000,000.00	1		
2	Payment	02/15/2026	348,442.95	180	Monthly	01/15/2041

Amortization Schedule - Normal, 365 Day Year

	Date	Payment	Interest	Principal	Balance
Loan	01/15/2026				40,000,000.00
1	02/15/2026	348,442.95	216,666.67	131,776.28	39,868,223.72
2	03/15/2026	348,442.95	215,952.88	132,490.07	39,735,733.65
3	04/15/2026	348,442.95	215,235.22	133,207.73	39,602,525.92
4	05/15/2026	348,442.95	214,513.68	133,929.27	39,468,596.65
5	06/15/2026	348,442.95	213,788.23	134,654.72	39,333,941.93
6	07/15/2026	348,442.95	213,058.85	135,384.10	39,198,557.83
7	08/15/2026	348,442.95	212,325.52	136,117.43	39,062,440.40
8	09/15/2026	348,442.95	211,588.22	136,854.73	38,925,585.67
9	10/15/2026	348,442.95	210,846.92	137,596.03	38,787,989.64
10	11/15/2026	348,442.95	210,101.61	138,341.34	38,649,648.30
11	12/15/2026	348,442.95	209,352.26	139,090.69	38,510,557.61
2026 Totals		3,832,872.45	2,343,430.06	1,489,442.39	

Cost Segregation Study Results:

Description	Date Placed In Service	Amount	Current Year Depreciation
5 Year Property	2/1/2026	\$ 8,474,742	\$ 1,694,948
7 Year Property	2/1/2026	\$ 59,831	\$ 8,547
15 Year Property	2/1/2026	\$ 3,524,757	\$ 234,984
39 Year Property	2/1/2026	\$ 27,940,670	\$ 716,427
Totals		\$ 40,000,000	\$ 2,654,907

Accounting Journal Entries:

Date	Account and Description	Debit	Credit
01/15/2026	Cash	\$10,050,000	
	Split Entry, Capital Contributions		\$10,050,000
	To record cash contributed to open bank account		
01/15/2026	Building 5 Year Property	\$8,474,742	
	Building 7 Year Property	\$59,831	
	Building 15 Year Property	\$3,524,757	
	Building 39 Year Property	\$27,940,670	
	Land	\$10,000,000	
	Escrow	\$50,000	
	Mortgage Payable		\$40,000,000
	Cash		\$10,050,000
	To record acquisition of real estate with mortgage		
01/15/2026	Consulting Expense	\$15,000	
	Credit Card Payable		\$15,000
	To record consulting fee for cost segregation study		
02/01/2026	Cash	\$400,000	
	Rental Income		\$400,000
	To record rental income received		
02/07/2026	Mortgage Payable	\$131,776.28	
	Interest Expense	\$216,666.67	
	Escrow	\$35,416.66	
	Cash		\$383,859.61
	To record mortgage payment		

Date	Account and Description	Debit	Credit
06/15/2026	Cash	\$50,000	
	Split Entry, Capital Contributions		\$50,000
	To record cash contributed to purchase new AC system		
06/16/2026	AC System	\$50,000	
	Cash		\$50,000
	To record purchase of AC system		
12/31/2026	Real Estate Taxes	\$350,000	
	Escrow		\$350,000
	To record adjustment for real estate taxes		
12/31/2026	Insurance	\$75,000	
	Escrow		\$75,000
	To record adjustment for insurance		
12/31/2026	Depreciation Expense	\$2,654,907	
	Accumulated Depreciation		\$2,654,907
	To record depreciation on building		
12/31/2026	Depreciation Expense	\$50,000	
	Accumulated Depreciation		\$50,000
	To record depreciation on AC system		
12/31/2026	Credit Card Payable	\$15,000	
	Cash		\$15,000
	To pay off credit card		
12/31/2026	Split Entry, Capital Distributions	\$150,000	
	Cash		\$150,000
	To record distribution of profit from rental activity		

Financial Statements:

123 Anywhere Arizona LLC

Balance Sheet

As of December 31, 2026

Assets

Current Assets

Cash \$ 12,544

Escrow \$ 14,583

Total Current Assets \$ 27,128

Fixed Assets

Building \$ 40,000,000

Land \$ 10,000,000

AC System \$ 50,000

Accumulated Depreciation \$ (2,704,907)

Total Fixed Assets \$ 47,345,093

Total Assets \$ 47,372,221

Liabilities and Members' Equity

Liabilities - Mortgage Payable \$ (38,510,558)

Members' Equity

Members' Contributions \$ (10,100,000)

Members' Distributions \$ 150,000

Net Loss \$ 1,088,337

Total Members' Equity \$ (8,861,663)

Total Liabilities and Members' Equity \$ (47,372,221)

123 Anywhere Arizona LLC

Statement of Operations

For the 12 Months Ended December 31, 2026

Rental Income	\$ (4,400,000)
Expenses	
Consulting Expense	\$ 15,000
Interest Expense	\$ 2,343,430
Real Estate Taxes	\$ 350,000
Insurance	\$ 75,000
Total Expenses	<u>\$ 2,783,430</u>
Income from Operations	\$ (1,616,570)
Depreciation Expense	\$ 2,704,907
Net Loss	<u><u>\$ 1,088,337</u></u>

Empirical Analysis: The Real-World Impact of Cost Segregation on Residential Rentals

Research Objective: To empirically measure the average tax impact and reallocation percentages achieved through engineering-based cost segregation studies across various residential real estate asset types.

Methodology:

This analysis relies on aggregated, anonymized financial data sourced from three distinct cost segregation studies conducted on residential properties. By comparing the baseline straight-line depreciation to the accelerated MACRS depreciation achieved through the studies, we can observe the tangible first-year tax benefits and identify consistent allocation trends.

Observed Data Summary:

The following table details the baseline data and reallocated basis for three observed residential properties, encompassing a multi-family property, a single-family home, and a condo unit:

Metric	Property A (Multi-Family, NM)	Property B (Single-Family, CA)	Property C (Condo, AZ)
Purchase Price	\$750,000	\$679,000	\$306,000
Depreciable Basis	\$566,927	\$543,200	\$244,800
Reallocated to 5-Year	\$120,114	\$47,585	\$71,827
Reallocated to 7-Year	\$848	\$339	\$557
Reallocated to 15-Year	\$49,957	\$122,027	\$1,641
Total Accelerated Basis	\$170,919	\$169,951	\$74,025
% of Basis Accelerated	30.15%	31.29%	30.24%

Scenario Analysis and Empirical Findings:

- **Remarkable Consistency Across Asset Types:** Despite differing geographical locations, price points, and specific residential types (multi-family vs. single-family vs. condo), the empirical data demonstrates an incredibly consistent reallocation rate. All three properties successfully segregated approximately **30% to 31%** of their total depreciable basis into shorter recovery periods.
- **The Bonus Depreciation Multiplier:** Both Property B and Property C provide empirical evidence of the massive impact of tax code timing. Because Property C was placed in service in June 2022, it qualified for the 100% bonus depreciation rate. Consequently, instead of merely accelerating the timeline, the investor was able to deduct the entirety of the 5, 7, and 15-year property in Year 1.
- **Actual Year 1 Deduction Validation:** Without cost segregation, Property C's straight-line deduction for the partial year would have been roughly \$3,365. With the study and bonus depreciation applied, the actual Year 1 deduction spiked to **\$77,390**.

Conclusion:

The aggregated empirical data verifies that engineering-based cost segregation studies predictably reclassify roughly 30% of a residential property's basis, regardless of the property's size or specific sub-type. When combined with bonus depreciation provisions, this strategy transforms paper losses into massive, immediate tax relief, thereby drastically improving the investor's Year 1 cash flow.

Return on Investment (ROI) of the Cost Segregation Strategy

Objective: To empirically determine if the upfront capital required to commission an engineering-based cost segregation study is financially justified by the Year 1 tax savings.

Methodology for ROI Calculation:

To calculate the actual financial benefit to the investor, we must isolate the *additional* depreciation generated exclusively by the study. We achieve this by subtracting the baseline straight-line depreciation (the control) from the accelerated depreciation (the observed result). We then apply a hypothetical effective tax rate of 32% to determine the actual cash saved on the investor's tax return.

Note: For the purposes of this analysis, we assume a standard residential engineering consulting fee of \$2,500 per study.

Empirical ROI Data:

Metric	Property A (Multi-Family)	Property B (Single-Family)	Property C (Condo)
Actual Year 1 Depreciation	\$35,644	\$173,911	\$77,390
<i>*Control (Straight-Line) **</i>	\$12,884	\$5,761	\$4,821
Added Depreciation	\$22,760	\$168,150	\$72,569
Estimated Tax Savings (32%)	\$7,283	\$53,808	\$23,222
Estimated Cost of Study	\$2,500	\$2,500	\$2,500
Net Cash Flow Increase	\$4,783	\$51,308	\$20,722
First-Year ROI	191%	2,052%	828%

**Control depreciation is calculated using the straight-line method over 27.5 years, prorated for the actual months the property was placed in service during Year 1.*

ROI Analysis and Conclusions:

- **Immediate Profitability:** In all three empirical cases, the tax savings generated in the first year entirely eclipsed the cost of the engineering study. Even in the most conservative scenario (Property A, which did not utilize 100% bonus depreciation), the investor nearly tripled their investment in the study, yielding a 191% first-year ROI.
- **The Bonus Depreciation Effect on ROI:** Properties B and C illustrate the exponential power of combining cost segregation with 100% bonus depreciation. By allowing the investors to deduct the entirety of their 5, 7, and 15-year property immediately, the ROI skyrocketed to 828% for the condo and over 2,000% for the single-family home.
- **Scalability:** Property C proves that cost segregation is not reserved strictly for multi-million-dollar commercial assets. Despite having a modest purchase price of \$306,000, the study generated over \$23,000 in actual tax savings, proving the strategy is highly scalable and lucrative for smaller residential investments.

Final Empirical Verdict:

The data overwhelmingly supports the use of engineering-based cost segregation studies. Across varying asset sizes and tax years, the upfront cost of the study is a statistically negligible expense compared to the massive, immediate increase in after-tax cash flow.

Glossary

Term	Basic Definition
Accounting	The language of business; a process of recording, summarizing, and reporting financial transactions for a business or person.
Amortization Schedule	A detailed table that shows the repayment of a loan over its term, including monthly payments, interest, principal, and ending balances.
Asset	Something valuable owned by a business, such as cash, equipment, or property.
Capital	The money or other assets invested in a business by its owners.
Cash	Money in the form of currency or funds held in checking or savings accounts.
Cash basis	An accounting method where income and expenses are recorded only when cash is received or paid.
Commercial Real Estate	Property used for business activities, like office buildings or shopping centers.
Corporation	A legal business structure owned by shareholders, separate from its owners.
Cost Segregation Study	An IRS-approved tax strategy that accelerates depreciation deductions for real estate activity
Credit	An entry on the right side of an account, usually meaning money is received or a liability increases.
Current Asset	An asset expected to be converted to cash or used up within one year, like inventory or receivables.
Current Liability	A debt or obligation due to be paid within one year.
De Minimis Rule	A tax rule allowing small expenses, typically less than \$2,500, to be deducted instead of capitalized.
Debit	An entry on the left side of an account, usually meaning money is spent or an asset increases.
Depreciation	The process of spreading the cost of a fixed asset over its useful life.
Earned Income	Money received for work performed, such as wages or salary.
Equity	The owner's interest in a business, calculated as assets minus liabilities.
Escrow	Money held by a third party until certain conditions are met, often used in real estate transactions.

Expense	The cost of goods or services used to operate a business.
Fixed Asset	A long-term asset used in business operations, like buildings or machinery.
Insurance Expense	The cost paid for insurance coverage.
Interest Expense	The cost of borrowing money, paid as interest on loans.
Liability	An amount owed by a business to others, like loans or unpaid bills.
Long Term Liability	A debt or obligation that is due in more than one year.
Loss	When expenses are greater than income, resulting in negative profit.
Mortgage	A loan used to buy real estate, with the property used as collateral.
Paper Loss	A loss shown on paper, based on the non-cash deductions, such as depreciation, with operations actually resulting in positive cash flow, but a reportable loss for tax purposes.
Partnership	A business owned by two or more people who share profits and losses.
Passive Income	Money earned from investments or activities not actively managed, like rental income.
Portfolio Income	Earnings from investments like stocks, bonds, or mutual funds.
Profit	What remains after all expenses are subtracted from revenue.
Real Estate Taxes	Taxes paid on property ownership, usually to local governments.
Rental income	Money received from renting out property or equipment.
Residential Real Estate	Property used for housing, like houses or apartments.
Return on Investment (ROI)	A financial metric that evaluates the profitability or efficiency of an investment. To calculate ROI, you divide the net return (the profit) of an investment by its initial cost.
Revenue	The total amount of money earned from business activities before expenses.
Sole Proprietor	A business owned and run by one person, with no legal distinction between owner and business.
Tax Planner Projection	A plan to forecast and manage tax payments.
Tax Preparation	The process of preparing and filing tax returns.

Tax Strategy	A strategy to minimize taxes owed using legal methods and rules, such as creating a paper loss through real estate investing.

About the Author:

Michael Martin is an accountant with over 20 years tax and accounting experience who is a true native of Phoenix, Arizona, USA. His work experience includes working in tax and accounting focusing on corporate tax and controllership services, with specialized training in Real Estate investments. His education includes a BA from Trinity International University, where he majored in business with an emphasis in accounting (class of 2006). Through Keller Graduate School of Management of DeVry University, he earned an MS in Accounting (2016), Graduate Certificate in business intelligence and analytics management (2018), and MBA (2023).

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